

Yield ability of tillers separated from standing transplanted aman rice and replanted

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To help farmers in postflood agricultural rehabilitation when new seedlings are not available, we conducted an experiment using rice tillers separated

from a standing crop. We examined the number of tillers/hill needed for an economic yield and using old seedlings for late planting. In fields that had been planted with 45-d-old BR11 seedlings, we pulled the hill 35 d after transplanting and separated the tillers with roots. The uprooted tillers were replanted 17 Sep 1987 at 1, 3, 5, and 7 tillers/hill. Control was 65-d-old seedlings.

Soil was silty loam with pH 6.0-6.5. Plots were 5 × 3 m in a randomized

block design with 4 replications. All plots were fertilized with 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha, using urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Tiller counts were done at 2-wk intervals from 10 randomly selected hills/plot. Grain and straw yield was measured at 15% moisture.

It is possible to multiply seedlings by detaching tillers from mother hills and replanting at 3 tillers/hill (see table).

Planting 65-d-old seedlings could cause heavy yield loss. □

Plant development, yield components, yield, and harvest index (HI) of replanted tillers of transplanted Mukta rice in Bangladesh. ^a

Treatment	Days to		Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)		1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)		HI
	Flowering	Maturity			Filled	Unfilled		Grain	Straw	
65-d-old seedlings	74	104	88.0	266	93	21	21.62	3.8	7.1	0.35
Retransplanted 1 tiller/hill	68	99	100.5	218	149	21	20.78	4.4	5.5	0.44
Retransplanted 3 tillers/hill	62	96	100.3	228	149	22	21.00	5.3	5.3	0.48
Retransplanted 5 tillers/hill	59	91	105.0	230	147	23	21.20	5.3	5.0	0.51
Retransplanted 7 tillers/hill	56	87	106.8	228	149	24	21.35	5.2	5.2	0.50
LSD (0.05)	1	2	4.2	10.2	10	ns	ns	0.938	1.2	—
CV (%)	1.5	1.3	2.6	2.7	4.7	9.6	3.2	12.2	13.3	—

^a Mean of 4 replications. ns = not significant.

Effect of Triaccontanol on rice seedling weight and grain yield

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Triaccontanol has been found to stimulate growth of several crop plants. We treated seeds of rice cultivars Jaya, IR20, and Mukthi with Triaccontanol (source: Trianol-CF) at 3 concentrations: 0.01, 0.1, and 1.00 ppm.

Seeds were soaked 1 h just before seeding in pots containing evenly mixed soil. Biomass weight was measured 22 d after seeding. Seedlings treated at 0.01 and 0.10 ppm were superior to those with no Triaccontanol (Table 1).

In a field experiment, IR54R seedlings were sprayed with the same concentrations of Triaccontanol, at 3 d before transplanting (15 Mar 1988), at maximum tillering (15 Apr), and at grain ripening (3 Jun). Grain yield increased slightly with all treatments (Table 2). Tillering capacity did not

Table 2. Grain yield of IR54R treated with Triaccontanol.

Triaccontanol (ppm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0.01	10.2
0.10	9.8
1.00	9.7
0 (control)	8.9
CV (%)	2.7
LSD	0.4

change, but 1,000-grain weight was higher with 0.01 ppm. □

Table 1. Dry weight 22 d after sowing of 3 rice varieties grown in pots after 1-h seed treatment with Triaccontanol.

Triaccontanol (ppm)	Biomass (mg dry wt/plant)		
	IR20	Jaya	Mukthi
0.01	248	271	410
0.10	309	292	399
1.00	216	249	309
0 (control)	231	226	318
CV (%)	11.3	9.1	11.5
LSD	19	14	17

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Large granule urea efficiency in rice

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With increasing fertilizer prices, it has become important to increase the efficiency of applied fertilizer without additional cost. One technique is to use modified large size or large granule urea (LSU/LGU). We studied the performance of LSU/LGU (6-8 mm) in